

A framework for consistent definition and use of LSFs in AF/BP/RP/RVS

prepared by: L. Lindegren
affiliation : Lund Observatory
approved by:
reference: GAIA-C3-TN-LU-LL-080-02
issue: 2
revision: 0
date: 2009-06-26
status: Issued

Abstract

This note deals with several issues related to the definition, calibration and simulation of the Line Spread Function in the different Gaia instruments. (1) A general definition of the LSF is proposed. This is valid in the dispersive instruments of Gaia (BP, RP and RVS) as well as in the non-dispersive SM and AF, and for arbitrary spectra. (2) The terms ‘centroid’, ‘origin’ and ‘location’ are defined in relation to the LSF. (3) Conventions for fixing the origin of the LSFs in the different instruments are discussed. (4) The decomposition of arbitrary spectral energy distributions (SEDs) in terms of spectral basis functions is discussed. The spectral decomposition of the SED in wavelength space leads to a corresponding decomposition of the LSF in sample space. The important point here is that resulting decompositions in AF, BP and RP are all consistent with a single SED, which may be estimated from the BP and RP spectra. (5) A numerical example illustrates the spectral decomposition and the corresponding basis functions in sample space.

Document History

Issue	Revision	Date	Author	Comment
2	0	2009-06-26	LL	Equation (2) and preceding paragraph corrected
1	0	2009-05-14	LL	Minor corrections
D	1	2009-05-10	LL	Second draft
D	0	2009-04-18	LL	First draft

1 Definition of the Line Spread Function (LSF)

Let u be the along-scan (AL) coordinate expressed in pixels, although not restricted to integer values. It is assumed that, when a point object of the arbitrary spectral energy distribution¹ (SED) F is being observed in one of the Gaia instruments, there exists a continuous function $L(u|F)$, such that the observed pixel (or sample) values, corrected for the background, are proportional to $L(k - \kappa|F)$. Here k (integer) is the pixel coordinate of the sample and κ the location of the image. The charge distortion is here neglected, although it introduces a further modification of the sampled data.

It is understood that $L(u|F)$ may depend on other things besides F , notably the field index, position in the field, and the AL attitude rate error; but since this note deals exclusively with the SED dependence, these other factors are left out of the notation. Note however that, by definition, the LSF cannot depend on the magnitude of the star; thus $L(u|sF) = L(u|F)$ for any $s > 0$.

For non-dispersed images, the above definition agrees completely with the accepted concept of a Line Spread Function (LSF), with $u = 0$ representing the ‘origin’ of the LSF, and κ the corresponding ‘location’ of the image in the sample stream (see Sect. 2). For dispersed images, as in BP, RP and RVS, the function $L(u|F)$ represents the observed, normalized spectrum, and is usually not thought of as a Line Spread Function. Conceptually, there is however no difference between the definition of the LSF depending on whether the image is dispersed or not. Indeed, even in AF there is usually some small dispersion present (called chromaticity). The main difference is that the dependence of $L(u|F)$ on F is intentionally much stronger in BP, RP and RVS than it is in AF.

The above operational definition of the Line Spread Function must be complemented by two constraints that fix the scaling and origin of the function. The choice of origin is discussed in Sect. 3. The scaling is fixed by requiring

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} L(u|F) du = 1 \quad (1)$$

This normalization implies that the part of the Point Spread Function (PSF) that falls outside the transmitted window in the across-scan (AC) direction is *not* included in the LSF, while the part that is within the AC window but outside the AL window *is* included. The practical consequence of this convention is that the AC flux loss must be accounted for in the photometric calibration, while the AL flux loss is automatically taken into account in the image parameter estimation (through the LSF fitting).

In the following, the LSF will sometimes be written $L(u)$ for conciseness, thus omitting the explicit dependence on F , although such a dependence is always present.

¹The generic function F (for ‘flux’) represents the spectral density of photons reaching Gaia from a given star. The notation F^λ will be used when the photon density must be expressed per unit wavelength.

FIGURE 1: Definition of centroid, origin and location: the top diagram shows a schematic LSF with the origin ($u = 0$) and centroid ($u = u_0$) indicated. The bottom diagram shows the location (κ) of the LSF in the stream of sample values N_k . In this case the scene consists of a uniform background of brightness β (in electrons per sample) plus a single point source of intensity α (in electrons) at $k = \kappa$.

2 Definition of the centroid, origin and location of the LSF

Words like ‘centroid’, ‘centroiding’, ‘LSF zero point’, ‘location’ are sometimes used without being clearly defined or with different meanings depending on the context or author. A common, agreed terminology would help to clarify some important concepts.

For any continuous LSF, $L(u)$, the following usage is proposed:

- *Centroid*: this is an intrinsic property of the LSF. For a symmetric LSF it is naturally given by the point of symmetry, i.e., if u_0 is such that $L(u_0 - u) = L(u_0 + u)$ for any u , then u_0 is the centroid of $L(u)$. For non-symmetric functions a more general definition is needed. At least for AF, it is recommended to always use the centroid defined by Tukey’s biweight Lindegren (LL-068), in which case u_0 is the solution of the non-linear equation

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} L(u_0 + u)w(u/s) du = 0 \quad (2)$$

for $s = 2.7$, where

$$w(z) = \begin{cases} z(1 - z^2)^2 & \text{if } |z| < 1 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The reasons for this particular choice of $w(z)$ and s are extensively discussed in Lindegren (LL-068). Since $w(z)$ is an odd function, u_0 will be the symmetry point for any symmetric LSF. For the BP, RP and RVS, this centroid definition is only suitable for a monochromatic or quasi-monochromatic SED.

- *Origin*: this is an agreed reference point ($u = 0$) for the LSF. It could be the centroid, but in general it is not. The choice of origin is discussed in subsequent sections.
- *Location*: this is the coordinate (κ) of the fitted LSF in the sample stream (k).

The different concepts are schematically illustrated in Fig. 1. They can trivially be generalized to the two-dimensional case of a Point Spread Function (PSF) by separate application to the marginal functions, i.e., to the along-scan LSF and across-scan LSF.

A consequence of these distinctions is that the term ‘centroiding’ should be reserved for the process of finding the centroid of a given LSF, i.e. of solving u_0 from Eq. (2). The process of estimating κ (the location) by fitting a given LSF to sample data should most properly be called ‘location estimation’. However, since usually other parameters are estimated in the same process (in particular the intensity, i.e., the total number of electrons in the image), a more general term could be ‘image parameter estimation’.

One may ask why it is necessary to distinguish between the centroid and origin of the LSF, i.e., why not simply agree that the origin is always taken to be the centroid? There are very good physical reasons why the distinction is necessary. For the astrometric observations, it is necessary that the location derived by fitting the calibrated LSF to the sample data must correspond to a physically well-defined celestial direction (α, δ). Due to the chromaticity, this is not possible if we use the centroid to define the origin, because the location would then be a function of the SED. Although for single stars this could be calibrated away in the astrometric solution (by including chromatic calibration terms), it would create big problems when analyzing for example a binary, if the components have different SEDs. Therefore, the LSF origin must be achromatic, which implies that it cannot always coincide with the centroid.

3 Fixing the origin of the LSF

The theoretical calculation of $L(u|F)$ could be done in several steps:

1. For a given WFE map and wavelength λ , the monochromatic optical LSF $L_\lambda^O(u)$ can be calculated by the Fraunhofer diffraction formula (see for example Eq. 8 in Lindegren (GAIA-LL-046)).

2. The effective monochromatic LSF $L_\lambda(u)$ is then obtained by taking into account pixel integration, TDI smearing, electron diffusion, etc. It is assumed that these effects can be described as linear convolutions, so that the net effect is

$$L_\lambda(u) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} L_\lambda^O(u - u') \Pi_\lambda(u') \, du' \quad (4)$$

where $\Pi_\lambda(u)$ represents all the different smearing effects mentioned above (but not the CTI, which is non-linear). $\Pi_\lambda(u)$ depends (slightly) on wavelength because the electron diffusion is wavelength dependent.² In line with the previously introduced notation, we could have written $L_\lambda(u) = L(u|\delta_\lambda)$, where δ_λ is the monochromatic SED of wavelength λ .

3. Finally, the effective polychromatic LSF for the arbitrary SED F is obtained as a photon-weighted average of $L_\lambda(u)$ over all wavelengths:

$$L(u|F) = \frac{\int_0^\infty L_\lambda [u - D(\lambda)] F^\lambda(\lambda) R(\lambda) \, d\lambda}{\int_0^\infty F^\lambda(\lambda) R(\lambda) \, d\lambda} \quad (5)$$

where $D(\lambda)$ is the dispersion function expressed in pixels. That is, at wavelength λ the AL displacement of $L_\lambda(u)$ is $D(\lambda)$ pixels. Here, $R(\lambda) = T(\lambda)Q(\lambda)$ is the total spectral response of the instrument, i.e., the product of the transmittance and quantum efficiency.

Any consistent calculation of the sample values in AF, BP, RP or RVS must use formulae that are effectively equivalent to Eqs. (4)–(5), even though the actual implementation could vary.

However, there is a serious ambiguity in this whole process related to the definitions of the dispersion function $D(\lambda)$ and the zero points of the effective monochromatic LSF $L_\lambda(u)$.

It is evident from Eq. (5) that the resulting $L(u|F)$ is invariant to any shift of the origin of $L_\lambda(u)$, as long as the same shift is applied to $D(\lambda)$. Moreover, the shift can be an arbitrary function of wavelength. Thus, depending on the definition of the origin of $L_\lambda(u)$ as function of wavelength, $D(\lambda)$ can in fact become any function that we want, even $D(\lambda) = 0$ (no dispersion)!

In the simulations, this ambiguity does not matter as long as the origin and dispersion function are consistently defined. For example, the origin of the LSF could be given by the chief ray in the optical ray tracing, provided that the same ray is used to define $D(\lambda)$. This approach is not invalidated by the circumstance that we cannot find out from the observations where the chief ray is.

²In reality the calculation of $L_\lambda^O(u)$ and its subsequent convolution with $\Pi_\lambda(u)$ are efficiently combined and calculated by means of the FFT as described in Babusiaux et al. (CB-002) and references therein.

For the data analysis, the situation is different. Here it is simply necessary to agree on a *convention* on how to distribute the shift between the LSF origin and the dispersion function. The convention need not be the same for the different instruments. Several options are possible:

1. We can agree that the origin should be achromatic, which implies $D(\lambda) = \text{constant}$. As already mentioned, this is the convention that must be used for AF (and SM).
2. We can agree that for any wavelength the origin should coincide with the centroid. As explained in Sect. 2, this is not acceptable for AF, but could be a valid option for BP, RP and RVS, at least for the (quasi-) monochromatic LSFs.
3. We can agree that $D(\lambda)$ is a fixed, nominal function, and any additional wavelength dependent shifts are absorbed by the origins of the monochromatic LSFs. Again, this could be a valid option for BP, RP and RVS. Option 1 adopted for AF is a special case of this.
4. A number of ‘mixed’ conventions could also be contemplated, but they are probably not relevant for the data analysis (whereas they could be the natural choice for simulations, as explained above).

The choice of Option 1 for AF is thus clear, but for BP, RP and RVS the choice is not so obvious. Since it is very difficult to calibrate the LSF as function of wavelength in these instruments, one probably wants to make the LSF as little dependent on wavelength as possible, which would tend to favour Option 2. Nevertheless, the spectral decomposition of the LSF discussed below seems to favour an achromatic origin also for the BP and RP.

Having adopted Option 1 for AF, the LSF origin is still undefined with respect to a constant (wavelength-independent) shift. This must be fixed by requiring that the LSF origin coincides with the centroid (as defined by Eqs. 2–3) for a certain reference SED:

$$L(u|F_{\text{ref}}) = L(u - u_0|F_{\text{ref}}) \quad (6)$$

The exact choice of F_{ref} is uncritical, but it is probably advantageous if it corresponds to one of the most common SEDs among the primary astrometric stars.

4 Spectral decomposition of the SED and LSF

The definition of $L(u|F)$ in terms of arbitrary SEDs provides a unified framework for dealing with monochromatic, quasi-monochromatic and polychromatic LSFs. We have already noted that the monochromatic LSF in Eq. (4) equals $L(u|F)$ for the monochromatic SED, $F^\lambda = \delta_\lambda$.

Any given SED can be approximated by a linear combination of *spectral basis functions* $B_i^\lambda(\lambda)$,

$$F^\lambda(\lambda) \simeq \sum_i f_i B_i^\lambda(\lambda) \quad (7)$$

where f_i are spectral coefficients. There is considerable freedom in choosing the basis functions, but they should at least satisfy the two conditions,

$$B_i^\lambda(\lambda) \geq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \int_0^\infty B_i^\lambda(\lambda) d\lambda = 1 \quad (8)$$

A practically useful set would obviously need to satisfy several more conditions. The linear (triangular-shaped) B-splines from Lindegren (SAG-LL-025,L) is a possible set, but the precise choice is irrelevant for the present discussion.

Using the above spectral decomposition, the two integrals in Eq. (5) become

$$\int_0^\infty L_\lambda [u - D(\lambda)] F^\lambda(\lambda) R(\lambda) d\lambda \simeq \sum_i f_i \int_0^\infty L_\lambda [u - D(\lambda)] B_i^\lambda(\lambda) R(\lambda) d\lambda \quad (9)$$

and

$$\int_0^\infty F^\lambda(\lambda) R(\lambda) d\lambda \simeq \sum_i f_i \int_0^\infty B_i^\lambda(\lambda) R(\lambda) d\lambda = \sum_i f_i r_i \quad (10)$$

where

$$r_i = \int_0^\infty B_i^\lambda(\lambda) R(\lambda) d\lambda \quad (11)$$

Therefore, if we define a corresponding set of basis functions for the LSF as

$$L_i(u) \equiv L(u|B_i^\lambda) = r_i^{-1} \int_0^\infty L_\lambda [u - D(\lambda)] B_i^\lambda(\lambda) R(\lambda) d\lambda \quad (12)$$

it follows that

$$L(u|F) \simeq \frac{\sum_i f_i r_i L_i(u)}{\sum_i f_i r_i} \quad (13)$$

The basis functions $L_i(u)$ can be seen as a generalization of the ‘quasi-monochromatic’ LSFs used in some earlier simulations.

5 Consistent spectral decomposition in AF, BP and RP

The spectral decomposition of the SED and LSF described in Sect. 4 allows to connect the different decompositions in AF, BP and RP in a consistent way. This is possible because (i) the spectral decomposition of the SED is done in terms of F^λ , which by definition is the same for a given object in all instruments, and (ii) the decomposition of the LSF is done in sample space

as required by the definition of the LSF, and (iii) the connection between the two is made via the functions $R(\lambda)$ and $D(\lambda)$, which in general are different for each instrument.

To illustrate this, let us consider the following problem: assuming a fully calibrated instrument, how can the effective wavenumber ν_{eff} (where $\nu = \lambda^{-1}$) in AF be computed from the observed samples in BP and RP? We use subscripts AF, BP and RP to distinguish the different spectral response functions $R(\lambda) = T(\lambda)Q(\lambda)$ and associated coefficients r_i . The observed samples in BP and RP (after correction for background) are modelled as

$$S^{\text{BP}}(k) = L^{\text{BP}}(k - \kappa|F) \times \int_0^\infty F^\lambda(\lambda) R^{\text{BP}}(\lambda) d\lambda \quad (14)$$

$$S^{\text{RP}}(k) = L^{\text{RP}}(k - \kappa|F) \times \int_0^\infty F^\lambda(\lambda) R^{\text{RP}}(\lambda) d\lambda \quad (15)$$

where F is the (as yet unknown) SED and κ is the known location of the spectra in the sample stream (here assumed to be the same in BP and RP). Using Eqs. (10) and (13) this can be written

$$\left. \begin{aligned} S^{\text{BP}}(k) &\simeq \sum_i f_i \times r_i^{\text{BP}} L_i^{\text{BP}}(k - \kappa) \\ S^{\text{RP}}(k) &\simeq \sum_i f_i \times r_i^{\text{RP}} L_i^{\text{RP}}(k - \kappa) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (16)$$

Therefore, if the functions $L_i^{\text{BP}}(u)$, $L_i^{\text{RP}}(u)$ and coefficients r_i^{BP} , r_i^{RP} are known from the calibrations, it is possible to estimate a unique set of spectral coefficients f_i from the combined BP and RP samples according to Eq. (16).

Note that $S^{\text{BP}}(k)$ or $S^{\text{RP}}(k)$ separately would not be sufficient to estimate all the coefficients f_i , while (16) provides the optimal combination of the data for estimating the full set of coefficients.³

The effective wavenumber in AF can now be computed as

$$\nu_{\text{eff}}^{\text{AF}} = \frac{\int_0^\infty F^\lambda(\lambda) R^{\text{AF}}(\lambda) \lambda^{-1} d\lambda}{\int_0^\infty F^\lambda(\lambda) R^{\text{AF}}(\lambda) d\lambda} \simeq \frac{\sum_i f_i r_i^{\text{AF}} \nu_i^{\text{AF}}}{\sum_i f_i r_i^{\text{AF}}} \quad (17)$$

where

$$r_i^{\text{AF}} = \int_0^\infty B_i^\lambda(\lambda) R^{\text{AF}}(\lambda) d\lambda \quad (18)$$

as in Eq. (11) and

$$\nu_i^{\text{AF}} = (r_i^{\text{AF}})^{-1} \int_0^\infty B_i^\lambda(\lambda) R^{\text{AF}}(\lambda) \lambda^{-1} d\lambda \quad (19)$$

³In the presence of radiation damage (CTI) effects, the estimation of f_i has to be done by applying the Charge Distortion Model (CDM) to the ‘undamaged’ sample values predicted by the right-hand side of Eq. (16) and fitting the CDM output to the observed counts. The procedure is equivalent to the image parameter estimation in AF, and is in principle straightforward, given a calibrated CDM.

is the effective wavenumber in band i . Similar expressions can be derived for any other function of F needed for example in the LSF calibration.

6 Choice of spectral basis functions

The choice of spectral basis functions $B_i^\lambda(\lambda)$ will depend on the application and could for example be different in the simulations (even between GIBIS and GASS) and in the various data analysis applications. The RVS is obviously very different from BP and RP in terms of resolution. Simulations could use a much finer grid of basis functions than the data analysis, where one would rather like to minimize the number of basis functions.

Generally speaking, the fewer basis functions are used for the decomposition, the more carefully they have to be chosen. As an example let us consider a decomposition of the BP and RP samples suitable for synthesis of the LSF in AF according to (16)–(17).

Triangular basis functions (B-splines of degree 1) Lindegren (SAG-LL-025,L), which effectively make a polygon approximation of the SED, are easy to define and use, and provide a good compromise between smoothness (favouring B-splines of a higher degree, e.g., quadratic or cubic) and independence of the spectral coefficients (favouring B-splines of degree 0, i.e., non-overlapping rectangular bands). The N triangular basis functions $B_i^\lambda(\lambda)$ ($i = 0, \dots, N-1$) are uniquely defined by the non-decreasing knot sequence $\lambda_0, \lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_{N+1}$ through⁴

$$B_i^\lambda(\lambda) = \frac{2}{\lambda_{i+2} - \lambda_i} \times \begin{cases} (\lambda - \lambda_i)/(\lambda_{i+1} - \lambda_i) & \text{if } \lambda_i \leq \lambda < \lambda_{i+1} \\ (\lambda_{i+2} - \lambda)/(\lambda_{i+2} - \lambda_{i+1}) & \text{if } \lambda_{i+1} \leq \lambda < \lambda_{i+2} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

The normalization factor ensures that the second equality in (8) holds, which means that f_i represents the flux in the i th, and $\sum_i f_i$ the total flux in the SED.

The placement of the knots near the wavelength cut-offs of the different response curves requires some care in order to avoid serious truncation errors when applying Eqs. (16)–(17). This is illustrated by the numerical example in Sect. 7. In particular, double knots should be used at the ends of the wavelength support interval (i.e., $\lambda_0 = \lambda_1$ and $\lambda_N = \lambda_{N+1}$) to allow a non-zero SED at these points. Note that the double knots will not cause division by zero in Eq. (20) provided that the inequalities are strictly tested.

⁴The indexing of the B-splines here differs from that in Lindegren (SAG-LL-025) and Marrese & Brown (PM-004), but agrees with Lindegren (LL-066) and the convention introduced in Lindegren (LL-070) for attitude splines, namely, that the B-spline is labelled with the same index as the left-most knot of its support.

FIGURE 2: Nominal response functions $R^{AF}(\lambda)$ (solid curve), $R^{BP}(\lambda)$ (long-dashed curve) and $R^{RP}(\lambda)$ (short-dashed curve). The vertical dotted lines indicate a possible knot sequence for 11 triangular basis functions (the extreme knots are double).

FIGURE 3: The basis functions $B_i^\lambda(\lambda)$ for the knot sequence in Fig. 2.

7 A numerical example

This section gives an example illustrating the decomposition of the SED into $N = 11$ triangular basis functions in wavelength space, and the corresponding decompositions of the observed BP and RP spectra in terms of LSF basis functions in sample space.

Figure 2 shows the nominal response functions in AF, BP and RP according to the current Gaia Parameter Data Base (GPDB). The vertical dotted lines show a possible knot sequence for the SED, taking into account the support and overlap of the different response functions. The knot sequence is

$$(\lambda_0, \dots, \lambda_{12}) = (330, 330, 390, 440, 550, 630, 650, 670, 780, 900, 1020, 1060, 1060) \text{ nm} \quad (21)$$

The corresponding spectral basis functions from (20) are shown in Fig. 3. Note how the double knots at the end points change the shape of the first and last basis function to infinite slope at the extreme wavelengths. This allows the spectral decomposition in Eq. (7) to represent for example a flat spectrum, $F^\lambda(\lambda) = \text{constant}$, over the entire wavelength interval where $R(\lambda) > 0$ in some instrument. The coefficients r_i calculated from Eq. (11) and the effective wavenumbers ν_i from Eq. (19) are given in Table 1.

The corresponding basis functions for the BP and RP line spread functions, computed from Eq. (12), are shown in Figs. 4–5. These were only computed for $i = 0 \dots 6$ in BP and for $i = 4 \dots 10$ in RP, r_i being negligible in other cases i according to Table 1. In this computation, the dispersion functions $D(\lambda)$ were taken from the GPDB (the fitted functions for FoV1, Row 4) and the monochromatic LSF was assumed to be a gaussian with standard deviation $\sigma = [(\lambda/(1000 \text{ nm}))^2 + 0.09]^{0.5}$ pixel. The dispersion functions are such that $D(\lambda_{\text{ref}}) = 0$ for $\lambda_{\text{ref}} = 440 \text{ nm}$ (BP) or 800 nm (RP), which therefore define the origins of the LSF basis functions.

The decomposition of the observed BP and RP spectra in terms of these LSF basis functions according to Eq. (16) provides an estimate of the spectral coefficients f_i , and hence of the SED, that fully takes into account the spectral smearing from the monochromatic LSFs. From the f_i it is then possible to compute various function of the SED, such as the effective wavenumber in AF, as described in Sect. 5.

Acknowledgement. The author wishes to thank C. Fabricius and A. Brown for valuable comments on earlier draft versions of this note.

FIGURE 4: Line spread functions $L_i^{\text{BP}}(u)$ (for $i = 0 \dots 6$) corresponding to the spectral decomposition in Fig. 3. The origin ($u = 0$) is the centroid of the monochromatic LSF for the BP reference wavelength $\lambda_{\text{ref}}^{\text{BP}} = 440$ nm.

FIGURE 5: Line spread functions $L_i^{\text{RP}}(u)$ (for $i = 4 \dots 10$) corresponding to the spectral decomposition in Fig. 3. The origin ($u = 0$) is the centroid of the monochromatic LSF for the RP reference wavelength $\lambda_{\text{ref}}^{\text{RP}} = 800$ nm.

TABLE 1: Coefficients r_i and effective wavenumbers ν_i (in μm^{-1}) calculated for the response functions in Fig. 2 and the basis functions in Fig. 3. The effective wavenumber is undefined when r_i is effectively zero.

i	r_i^{AF}	r_i^{BP}	r_i^{RP}	ν_i^{AF}	ν_i^{BP}	ν_i^{RP}
0	0.077754	0.111395	0.000000	2.80758	2.80666	–
1	0.202854	0.263108	0.000000	2.51461	2.52505	–
2	0.587687	0.590460	0.000000	2.15559	2.17178	–
3	0.732985	0.608663	0.000022	1.85622	1.86533	1.61672
4	0.737871	0.579066	0.033491	1.64230	1.64248	1.55841
5	0.712262	0.477732	0.549880	1.53891	1.54361	1.53356
6	0.649691	0.025206	0.660925	1.43440	1.51721	1.42976
7	0.506882	0.000011	0.651894	1.29535	1.47331	1.28494
8	0.244126	0.000000	0.409361	1.14233	–	1.13757
9	0.056242	0.000000	0.127003	1.04316	–	1.03111
10	0.000018	0.000000	0.023707	0.97804	–	0.96049

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